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A Geodynamically Consistent Approach to Residual Topography and Geoid Anomalies on the Convecting Mantle: Importance of Global Crustal Models

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While the isostatic compensation of crustal thickness and density heterogeneity provides the dominant contribution to Earth's observed topography, there nonetheless remains a substantial difference (the 'residual topography') between these two fields. This difference is a consequence of dynamic processes occurring within the mantle, most notably due to time-dependent vertical surface stresses driven by mantle convection. Mantle convection dynamics also produce differences between the observed geoid and the isostatic geoid generated by crustal heterogeneity: the 'residual geoid'. The joint consideration of both residual geoid and topography anomalies provides unique and fundamental global constraints on the amplitude and spatial distribution of density anomalies in the convecting mantle.

Despite the crucial role of isostasy in determining residual geoid and residual topography, accurate constraints depend heavily on the quality of the isostasy calculations. The classical theory of isostasy relies on a 1st-order treatment of hydrostatic equilibrium, which is not sufficiently accurate for the calculation of isostatic geoid anomalies on a compressible, self-gravitating mantle. Consequently, we present a geodynamically consistent approach that is based on the surface loading response (via dynamic kernels) calculated with a viscous flow model that incorporates a fully compressible mantle and core (given by the PREM reference model) with self-gravitation.

Another critical issue that remains outstanding is the accuracy inherent in global crustal heterogeneity models. Here we show that the differences between the residual geoid and topography fields predicted using CRUST1.0 (Laske et al. 2012) and the most recent ECM1 (Mooney et al. 2023) crustal heterogeneity models are substantial. We discuss the importance and implications of these differences in the context of determining the most accurate constraints on density anomalies in the convecting mantle.

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A Geodynamically Consistent Approach to Residual Topography and Geoid Anomalies on the Convecting Mantle: Importance of Global Crustal Models

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• **What is the problem?**

Observed Topography (ETOPO 1)

Isostatic Topography (CRUST 1.0)

Residual Topography (CRUST 1.0)

Residual topography and geoid provides global constraints on the amplitude and spatial distribution of density anomalies in the convecting mantle.

Questions

- **How large is the uncertainty in these constraints due to the crustal model uncertainty?**
- **How can isostasy be geodynamically consistent?**

• **Geodynamic observables and lateral density variations**

Corresponding kernel function

$$\delta O_\ell^m = f_\ell \int_b^a K_\ell(\eta; r') (\rho_1)_\ell^m(r') dr'$$

↓
Geodynamic observable
↑
Lateral density variation

- **Isostatic Topography**

Crust 1.0

ECM 1

Crust 2.0

- **Residual Topography**

• **Isostatic Geoid**

• **Residual Geoid**

Spherical Harmonics Power Spectrum Analysis

Residual Topography:

Residual Geoid:

Geodynamically Consistent Modelling of Crustal Isostasy

- Viscosity
- Compressibility
- Self-gravitating

- **Summary and Discussion**

- Residual topography and geoid is a manifestation of internal mantle dynamics (i.e. convection).
- Isostatic geoid is small, but not negligible! The resulting residual geoid must be used in combination with residual topography as constraint on the mantle density heterogeneity.
- Residual topography uncertainties due to different crustal models has often been overlooked.
- Uncertainties in the multi-layer crustal models lead to significant uncertainties in the residual topography.
- Classic 1st-order treatments of isostasy theory ignore important effects arising from the internal state of stress in the crust, mantle compressibility and self-gravitation.
- A geodynamically consistent treatment, based on a compressible treatment of viscous flow with self-gravitation, reveals significant differences relative to classical isostasy theory.

Thanks for your attention